

Research Article

Sustainable Education: the case of Nigeria

Akarue Okiemute Blessing

Department of Agricultural Science Education, College of Education, P.M.B 1251,
Warri-Delta State. EMAIL: blessingakarue4edu@gmail.com

Abstract

There is really no one single definition of sustainable education. It's not defined in the traditional sense, and people around the globe are searching 'what is sustainability. This article aims to explore Sustainable Education in Nigeria .The paper opted for a general review approach, covering literature which provides an overview of the concepts, benefits, challenges and strategies of making sustainable education possible in Nigeria.

Keywords, sustainable education, Benefits, challenges, strategies, Nigeria

Received: 10 Feb. 2017

Accepted: 28 July 2017

Introduction

In Nigeria, as noted by the Federal Ministry of Education (2005) in the constitutional provisions, the main responsibilities of the Federal government in basic education are in the realm of policy formulation, coordination and monitoring. Direct control by the Federal government is preponderantly at the tertiary level. Only a handful of institutions at the secondary level (the Unity Schools and technical colleges) enjoy federal direct control. The bulk of secondary schools in the country are under the purview of state governments which are also directly responsible for a considerable proportion of the nation's tertiary institutions. Local governments have statutory managerial responsibility for primary education, with the federal and state governments exercising appropriate oversight functions.

However there has recently been the issue of private individuals and cooperate bodies coming into the educational sector in Nigeria with a view of improving the quality of

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 – 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

education in the country by bringing a lot of innovation to make education be what it is supposed to be. This is because it has become evident that most of our graduate no longer fit into the emerging economy of the world with the traditional way of learning and that they must learn to think things differently.

The above issue has giving raise to what is referred to as sustainable education , however in some quarters the name is not the same but the message the same , to some it is education for sustainability, for others it education for sustainable development. However is still not very clear to most people what this kind of education really means. Sustainability means different things to different people. For example in the United States the K-12 classroom as noted by Wendy Church and Laura Skelton defined it broadly as the notion that a generation of people can consider sustaining themselves without inhibiting the ability of future generations to do so. But some people use the term “sustainability education” interchangeably with “environmental education”, sustainability differs from environmental education in that it necessarily includes environmental, social, and economic concerns. However for Wendy Church and Laura Skelton they preferred the broader term “global sustainability” which refers to applying the sustainability concept on a global as well as local level, recognizing that at this time in human development we are all very much connected.

The broad interconnected issues we often think about when talking about global sustainability are population, poverty, environment, consumption, conflict, and quality of life. Specific topics of current or historical interest, such as climate change, education or health, fall under the umbrella of these broad issues. In addition to these broad issues, there are several skills that many believe to be critical to global sustainability. These include: (i) Taking a global perspective, including a recognition that issues, people, and places are interconnected (ii) Understanding how systems operate (iii) Thinking critically and making informed decisions

According to Wendy Church and Laura Skelton the issue became prominent in the US when about a decade ago, the U. S. President's Council on Sustainable Development (1996) published Education for Sustainability: An Agenda for Action. This document articulated a clear vision and a Federal agenda for education for sustainability in formal and informal settings and was emphatic in calling for the presence of sustainability in the K-12 curriculum as well as in the preparation of teachers. Since that time, global sustainability has become increasingly prevalent in teaching. Corroborating this view, Wade (2008) noted that Since the Earth Summit in 1992, there has been a growing awareness of the need to address issues of sustainability and the terrain subsequently

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

seems to have become more favourable towards education for sustainability. But Governments were very slow to take the initiative on education for sustainability but that after the first Earth Summit with this role largely taken up by non-governmental organisations (NGOs) and committed activists, however the situation has change since then.

The situation might not be fantastic in developing nations like Nigeria and other African nations , were the educational system is basically traditional with most of the work is done by the teachers and unstable government policies . But the Nigerian government is beginning to think differently on the issues with a lots of development in the world economy, with issues such as climate change, gap between graduate and real world situations, the present government has started some level of reforms in the educational sector .

Finally the United Nations on the occasion of the UN Conference on Sustainable Development in 2012, the leaders of the international academic community are called upon to commit to the development of sustainable practices for Higher Education Institutions.

The aim of the 2012 UN Conference on Sustainable Development, or Rio+20, is to secure renewed political commitment for sustainable development, assess the progress to date and the remaining gaps in the implementation of the outcomes of the major summits on sustainable development, and address new and emerging challenges. They noted that since Higher Education Institutions educate and train decision makers, they play a key role in building more sustainable societies and creating new paradigms. As educational institutions, they have the mission to promote development through both research and teaching, disseminating new knowledge and insight to their students and building their capabilities. Given the objectives of Rio+20, Higher Education Institutions have a special responsibility to provide leadership on education for sustainable development.

Education for sustainable development aims at enabling everyone to acquire the values, competencies, skills and knowledge necessary to contribute to building a more sustainable society. This implies revising teaching content to respond to global and local challenges. It should also promote teaching methods that enable students to acquire skills such as interdisciplinary thinking, integrated planning, understanding complexity, cooperating with others in decision-making processes, and participating in local, national and global processes towards sustainable development.

It should be noted that at the end of the conference the countries agreed to support the following actions:

- **Teach sustainable development concepts**, ensuring that they form a part of the core curriculum across all disciplines so that future higher education graduates develop skills necessary to enter sustainable development workforces and have an explicit understanding of how to achieve a society that values people, the planet and profits in a manner that respects the finite resource boundaries of the earth. Higher Education Institutions are also encouraged to provide sustainability training to professionals and practitioners;
- **Encourage research on sustainable development issues**, to improve scientific understanding through exchanges of scientific and technological knowledge, enhancing the development, adaptation, diffusion and transfer of knowledge, including new and innovative technologies.
- **Green our campuses** by: i) reducing the environmental footprint through energy, water and material resource efficiencies in our buildings and facilities; ii) adopting sustainable procurement practices in our supply chains and catering services; iii) providing sustainable mobility options for students and faculty; iv) adopting effective programmes for waste minimization, recycling and reuse, and v) encouraging more sustainable lifestyles.
- **Support sustainability efforts** in the communities in which we reside, working with local authorities and civil society to foster more liveable, resource-efficient communities that are socially inclusive and have small environmental footprints.
- **Engage with and share results through international frameworks**, such as the UN Decade of Education for Sustainable Development, led by UNESCO, the UN University system, the UN Academic Impact, the Global Compact, the UN-supported Principles for Responsible Management Education initiative and the UN Environment Programme's Environmental Education and Training initiatives, in order to exchange knowledge and experiences and to report regularly on progress and challenges."

Concept of sustainable education

The word sustainable education is like a new concept but is it really new? Sterling (2001) had a discussion on what was referred to as "new education Briefing " in that meeting discussants were not sure of what it was all about and the following ensued and I quote

"It was early 2001, I and the publisher of the Schumacher Briefings and I were having a chat in his office about the title of the new education Briefing. I had just made a bid for 'Sustainable Education'. His reply was along the lines: 'surely, you mean "education for sustainable development", or "education for sustainability" don't you? Are you implying "education that lasts?" - it doesn't make a lot of sense' No', I said, 'I don't want to call it education 'for' anything, and yes, 'Sustainable Education' is exactly the title I

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

want'. The reason I went for this title, is that I wanted it to provoke a little cognitive dissonance and the question: 'what does that mean?' I wanted people to move from 'how do we educate for sustainable development' towards deeper attention to education itself: its paradigms, policies, purposes and practices (these are linked of course) and its adequacy for the age we find ourselves in" (Sterling 2001).

It is pertinent at this stage to defined the what sustainable education is all about. Sterling (2001) defined sustainable education as - "a change of educational culture, one which develops and embodies the theory and practice of sustainability in a way which is critically aware. It is therefore a transformative paradigm which values, sustains and realises human potential *in relation to* the need to attain and sustain social, economic and ecological well-being, recognising that they must be part of the same dynamic.

Corroborating this view GEF (2014) noted that nobody knows what sustainability education is all about .It's not defined in the traditional sense, and people around the globe are searching 'what is sustainability' for GEF Institute they tried to fill the gap on the definition and they came up to define sustainability education in a way that also defines the education they develop which is - Sustainability education utilizes applied learning models that connect real-world circumstances with the broader human concerns of environmental, economic, and social systems.

Sterling (2001) further noted that the concept of 'sustainable education', is a term which suggests not just a simple 'add-on' of sustainability concepts to some parts of the curriculum, but a cultural shift in the way we see education and learning. But that rather than just seeing it as a piecemeal, bolt-on, fragmentary response which leaves the mainstream otherwise untouched, it implies systemic change in thinking and practice, informed by what can be called more ecological thinking and values – essentially a new paradigm emerging around the poles of holism, systemic thinking, sustainability and complexity. This offers the possibility of education that is appropriate and responsive to the new systemic conditions of uncertainty and complexity that are reflected in the headlines every day; one that nurtures the increasingly important qualities of adaptability, creativity, self-reliance, hope and resilience in learners.

Sustainable education implies four descriptors: educational policy and practice which is sustaining, tenable, healthy and durable.

- *Sustaining*: it helps sustain people, communities and ecosystems;
- *Tenable*: it is ethically defensible, working with integrity, justice, respect and inclusiveness;

- *Healthy*: it is itself a viable system, embodying and nurturing healthy relationships and emergence at different system levels;
- *Durable*: it works well enough in practice to be able to keep doing it. (Sterling, 2008)

Similarly UNESCO (2005) now see sustainable education as education that enables people to foresee, face up to and solve the problems that threaten life on our planet' (UNESCO, 2005).

Benefits of sustainable education

Sterling, (2008) opined that it is quite unfortunate that, the term 'sustainable education', with a few welcome exceptions, has often been bundled in by writers as synonymous with 'sustainability education', 'education for sustainability' and 'education for sustainable development', but they are not the same thing.

GEF (2014) opined that it is interesting to note that everyone is talking about green jobs and the new green economy. What about the education that gets you there? Or, what if you need to learn sustainability concepts to stay competitive in your current employment? Thus GEF Institute has seen this type of education as that which incorporates hands-on learning strategies that make deep connections with what people are most familiar with in their homes, their workplace, and their communities with the outcomes become more meaningful and lasting. Summarily the benefit are as follows -

1 Developing critical minds

This type of education demands critical thinking, analytical writing, and multi-dimensional understanding that is often absent in traditional curriculum or training. These skills, developed by studying topics like energy technology or the economics of sustainability, and finally put people at an advantage in their workplace or in higher education classrooms.

2. Builds essential skills

Sustainability concepts can provide wonderful context for developing the skills of critical thinking, systems thinking, collaboration, and communication. A teacher who had incorporated sustainability lessons into his classroom noted that the nature of lessons on sustainability requires that students apply critical thinking skills and that they draw from their own experiences and world knowledge. The interactive characteristic of the activities invites the participation of all students." Because sustainability discussions involve current affairs and often complex global connections, the material can be used as a starting point for critical thinking exercises as students consider the many facets of an

issue. Climate change is a great example of this, as it involves both science and related complex social and economic issues.

3. **Transformational and Lasting change**

The above terms represent worthy developments but do not necessarily connote the need for deep change in educational values, assumptions and practices. In response to the crisis of unsustainability, most educators - and increasingly, politicians - will ask 'what learning needs to take place amongst students?'. This is a perfectly valid and important question, but it begs a prior and deeper question: what changes, and what learning needs to take place amongst policymakers, amongst senior management, amongst teachers, lecturers, support staff, amongst parents, amongst employers, etc., so that education itself can be more transformative and appropriate to our times? Hence we need a change that will affect the system as a whole.

4. **Developed citizens**

According to Wiese (2009) quoting Debra Rowe on the benefit of Sustainable Education noted that and i quote "Through incorporating education for sustainability into your classroom, you are helping your students create a more healthy, habitable and equitable world by helping them become active citizens."

Wiese (2009) emphasised that teaching Sustainability Concepts has benefited his students in that whether they think of environmental, economic, sociological, or religious issues when conversations about living sustainably arise, it remains clear that sustainability is an important albeit complex topic of discussion for the educational community. By embracing environmental sustainability as a vital topic within the classroom, students internalize the importance of a high quality of life through:

- Expanding awareness of how to create a more healthy and equitable world for all beings.
- Encouraging creative problem solving through hands-on experimentation.
- Stimulating ownership and responsibility in your students' personal and everyday actions as well as their social actions & decisions within their community.
- Empowering students to evaluate their actions and helping them make more consistent decisions that benefit all beings.
- Increasing critical thinking skills and deep problem solving by using cyclical reasoning and real-world examples to better understand class subject matter.

5 **Bringing about a deeper change**

There is a need for change which will involve a re-examination of assumptions - towards a shift of consciousness, a changed intelligence which is both connective and

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

collective. This is a deeper and systemic learning response, which needs to happen in three areas: personal, organisational and the community (social learning beyond formal education). The most resistant area is change in the institution and organisation but this is being squeezed by growing awareness of individuals at one level; and evident shifts in social values and behaviours at the level of community and public debate.

6. Improving students' performance

Improves student engagement in learning Distracted students are non-learning students; student engagement in learning is a key to academic success. We've seen that real-world sustainability issues can engage students in a way that other topics or contexts do not. While there is no hard data linking improved test scores to sustainability programming, there are reports that that link student engagement to improved academic performance. It has been shown that Using Student Engagement has Improve Adolescent Literacy (Learning Point Institute, North Central Regional Educational Laboratory 2005):

7. Developing a change that will lead to learning about learning' process

Sterling (2008) noted that the change will envision and take realisable, practicable steps in our own contexts. In essence, what we all are engaged in here is a critically important change order 'learning about learning' process; one which will directly affect the chances of a more sustainable future for all. The United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organisation (UNESCO) report also pointed out that in (2002), just as we have learnt to live unsustainably, we now need to learn how to live sustainably. Such learning for *respons-ibility* requires educational systems, institutions and educators to develop *response-ability* - that is, the competence and will to address the considerable challenge and opportunity that sustainability presents. Finally they reported that this is the context of bases for any meaningful discussion about the role of education in the 21st century.

9. Connects students to real life issues

One of the benefit of sustainable education is that it connects students to their community and inspires active citizenship. In an annual teacher surveys conducted on students, thus assessing their knowledge, beliefs, and behavior before and after learning about global sustainability in their classrooms. The result shows that there was a drastic improvement on the student's attitude. And worldviews after participating in global sustainability programming in their classrooms.

Below are some quotes by some students

"I used to say I wanted to make a difference when I grow up. After this [global sustainability unit] I realize that I can make a difference right now."

"I think more about the world and what my purpose is in it."

"It made me think about what is happening in the world and how much the way I live is affecting it. This unit really changed my insight on life and it really makes me want to try to do something."

10 Prepares students for challenges of the 21st Century

Another benefit of sustainable education is that it prepares students for challenges of the 21st Century. This reasons are not farfetched because of the usefulness of this concept. Therefore this is the reason while many sustainability educators would put as foremost motivation to teach global sustainability. In fact, this is why many educators enter the teaching profession in the first place.

Challenges of sustainable education

The challenges facing sustainable education are enormous and not all educators are equally enthusiastic or willing to commit to sustainability education. Those educators wishing to incorporate sustainability concepts into their classrooms often face resistance from other teachers or administrators in their educational setting. The obstacle we hear most often mentioned by educators is a lack of time – time to learn something new, or the time to introduce an idea external to the curriculum. However according ESD toolkit, and other authors the challenges **include the following but not limited to**

➤ **Increasing Awareness: SD is Essential**

The initial step in launching an ESD program is to develop awareness within the educational community and the public that reorienting education to achieve sustainability is essential. If government officials or school district administrators are unaware of the critical linkages between education and sustainable development, reorienting education to address sustainable development will not occur. When people realize that education can improve the likelihood of implementing national policies, regional land and resource management programs, and local programs, then education is in a position to be reoriented to help achieve sustainability.

➤ **Structuring and Placing SD in the Curriculum**

Each country faces a fundamental decision in addressing a sustainable education strategy. It thus becomes necessary for Countries must decide on a method of implementation. If it becomes necessary they can create another "add on" subject, (e.g., Sustainable Development, Environmental Education, or Population

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Education) or to reorient entire education programs and practices to address sustainable development. Nations also need to clarify whether their educators are being asked to teach *about* sustainable development or to change the goals and methods of education to *achieve* sustainable development.

➤ **Linking to Existing Issues: Educational Reform and Economic Viability**

The effectiveness of the world's educational systems is already critically debated in light of the changing needs of society. The current widespread acknowledgment of the need for educational reform may help advance Education Sustainable Development (ESD). If it can be linked to one or more priorities of educational reform, ESD could have a good chance for success. However, if promoters try to add another issue to an already over-burdened system, the chances of success are slim.

➤ **Education itself as a problem.**

Although the terrain seems more promising now for EfS, there are concerns from many EfS commentators, such as David Orr and Stephen Sterling, that progress is too slow and does not go far enough. In fact, Sterling feels that no less than a complete shift in the overall paradigm of education (and by implication society) will result in sustainability. For Sterling, education itself is often part of the problem: 'Far from being an agent of change, education often underpins individualism, unsustainable lifestyles and patterns of consumption, directly or by default' (Sterling, 2005).

➤ **Building Human Capacity**

The successful implementation of a new educational trend will require responsible, accountable leadership and expertise in both systemic educational change and sustainable development. We must develop realistic strategies to quickly create knowledgeable and capable leadership. It

➤ **Developing Financial and Material Resources**

Perhaps one of the greatest expenses of implementing ES will come with providing appropriate basic education. Meeting these goals will require hiring many more teachers. These new teachers must be trained, and current teachers must be retrained, to reorient their curriculums to address sustainability.

According to UNESCO World Education Report 2000 Two-thirds of the 123 countries has improve their allocation to education. Although governments are prioritizing education in terms of funding, how much of this funding is going to reorient education to address sustainability? One of the reasons why many experts perceive that little progress has been made regarding ES is that few financial resources have been dedicated to reorienting education to address sustainability. In fact, national and local governments have spent little on ES beyond improving basic education. (ESD toolkit 2014).

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

Developing a Creative, Innovative, and Risk-Taking Climate

In order to bring about the major changes required by ES, we need to nurture a climate of safety. Policymakers, administrators, and teachers will need to make changes, experiment, and take risks to accomplish new educational and sustainability goals. They need to have the authority and support of the educational community to change the status quo. Teachers must feel that the administration will support their efforts if parents or vested interest groups in the community question or criticize their initiatives. We need to develop and implement policy to ensure administrators and educators at all levels have the right to introduce new or controversial topics and pedagogical methods. Of course, an over-zealous few could abuse these rights; therefore, a system of checks and balances within professional guidelines and cultural context should also be in place. (ESD toolkit 2014)

Promoting Sustainability in Popular Culture

Perhaps the most difficult obstacle to address in implementing ES is that of popularity. While many countries agreed that ES is important, the themes of sustainability are not prevalent in popular cultures or governmental policies. This principles of sustainable education are not currently woven into daily life and governmental policy (ESD toolkit 2014).

Strategies for Integrating Sustainability into Education Global sustainability.

Effective Strategies for Integrating Sustainability into Education Global sustainability is currently incorporated in a wide variety of ways into classrooms, schools, districts, states, and in non-formal education settings. Some teachers are able to teach about sustainability as a stand-alone subject, either as part of a course or in some cases, full courses. Others work sustainability into their materials as the contextual basis for core subjects, or for various kinds of student projects.

Strategy 1: Sustainability as its own subject

In some cases, teachers and schools may be able to teach sustainability as a stand-alone subject, not necessarily tied to particular core content learning standards. There are different variations on this approach: sustainability may be the subject of an entire course, it may be taught as a thematic unit within a core subject course, or it may be incorporated as a single lesson.

Supplemental curriculum, particularly activity-based lessons, is a great way to insert sustainability into classrooms. Described below are two sustainability-based lessons, followed by teachers' comments about these activities. We have seen these

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

particular lessons adopted for use by teachers in middle and high schools, as well as in interdisciplinary settings.

Strategy 2: Sustainability as the context within which to teach core subjects Global sustainability

Sustainability as the context within which to teach core subjects Global sustainability provides an authentic and engaging context for teaching core subjects. We've seen this approach taken in particular by science and social studies teachers. For example, when teaching about chemical bonds, a chemistry teacher might discuss how carbon's chemical structure is connected to global climate change.

Strategy 3: Sustainability projects Project-based learning is incorporated into many schools

Sustainability projects Project-based learning is incorporated into many schools and the interest in this approach is growing, particularly for culminating/senior projects, 'Project Weeks', and to fulfill service learning requirements. Global sustainability provides an incredible platform from which to base a breath-taking array of projects.

Strategy 4: Sustainability at the school-wide or district level to guide institutional and curricular

Sustainability at the school-wide or district level to guide institutional and curricular innovation - thematic. They noted that in a handful of schools and districts their country, sustainability is becoming an integrating context for "greening" the facilities and curriculum across subjects and grades.

Conclusions

It has become clear that there is a wide range of activities across various sectors of the economy that normal academic training cannot address without us creating the awareness raising on issues of sustainability that will involve doing things in a better way-learning to live sustainably. This is because human beings are very adaptive and intelligent beings who have learned to live unsustainably in rather a short space of time. Time is of the essence as it has become clear that some of the effects of climate change are already unstoppable. Our challenge for the future well-being of the planet and of human life is to learn - very quickly - how to live sustainably. Therefore we must think of how to successfully implement Sustainable education. However to do this relevant stakeholders- governments at all levels, universities, colleges of education, polytechnics and

This work is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)
ISSN: 2141 - 4181 Science and Education Development Inst., Nigeria

secondary schools must plan ahead and develop strategies to address the above mentioned challenges so that the benefits can be fully realised. This will involve deliberate planning around these issues as well as issues particular to each state will increase the likelihood of successfully implementing Sustainable education and reorienting curriculum to achieve sustainability. Finally, it is important to note that sustainability education is most powerful when an action component, such as service learning, is included. When we teach using sustainability concept the results is really overwhelmingly.

Recommendations

Based on the presentation above the following recommendations is believed to help actualised the full benefits of sustainable education in Nigeria.

- (i) Government should provide adequate funding to the bodies concerned for effective implementation of sustainable education.
- (ii) The government in partnership with the teachers/lecturer should create awareness on the relevance of sustainable education to individuals through workshops, seminars and conferences.
- (iii) The teacher /instructors need to change the way they teach and thus make the students to do more of thinking on the issue facing us with a view of findings solution instead of they try to find the solutions for the students.
- (iv) There should be a systematically planned expansion, to match growth education with the evolution of national resources and management capacity to ensure sustainability.
- (v) Improved Funding, with particular attention to widening the bases of funding and with some emphasis on improving the internal capacity of institutions to generate and (more particularly) manage funds and non-financial resources.
- (vi) Relevant policy makers need to do a curriculum renewal thus a need for a closer look at existing curricular options, the pattern of organization of programmes (including enhanced curriculum integration and emphasis on core generic skills), teaching and learning methods, etc, to ensure greater coherence with the rapidly changing demands of the knowledge economy and the world at large.

References

- ESD Toolkit (2014) challenges and Barriers to Education for sustainable Development
- Federal Ministry of Education (2005). Nigeria Education Sector Diagnosis A Condensed Version A Framework for Re-Engineering the Education Sector Education Sector Analysis Unit
- Sterling, S (2001) *Sustainable Education – Re-Visioning Learning and Change*, Schumacher Society Briefing no. 6, Green Books, Dartington.
- Sterling, S (2008) *Sustainable Education –towards a deep learning response to unsustainability .issue 6 spring.*
- UNESCO (2002) *Education for Sustainability – From Rio to Johannesburg: Lessons learnt from a decade of commitment*, UNESCO, Paris.
- UNESCO (2005) *UN Decade for Education for Sustainable Development 2005-2014*: <http://unesdoc.unesco.org/images/0014/001403/140372e.pdf>.
- United Nations (2012) Higher Education Sustainability Initiative for Rio+20. UN Conference on Sustainable Development.
- Wade, R (2008) 'Education for sustainability: Challenges and opportunities', Policy & Practice: A *Development Education Review*, Vol. 6, Spring, pp. 30-48.
- Wiese,J.(2009) Sustainability Education Handbook The Benefits: Monday, 19 October 2009 14:41